

USING TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO ACHIEVE EDUCATIONAL OUTCOMES

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Abstract: The article discusses the specifics of using modern information technologies in the process of effective teaching English in educational institutions. This project examines the importance of using computers and Internet resources to increase students' motivation.

Keywords: computer technologies, teaching English, innovative, Internet, resources, tasks, stages of work.

In modern society, the role of foreign languages is becoming truly irreplaceable. Knowledge of a foreign language gives the opportunity to join the world culture, to use the full potential of the Internet resources. Nowadays, new information technologies are being intensively introduced into all spheres of our life, including the educational process.

In this regard, there is a need to develop a methodology for using computer information technologies in teaching a foreign language. New information pedagogical technologies are becoming part of the educational process. Using Internet resources in foreign language lessons is a relevant direction in methodology that requires new approaches and non-standard solutions. New information technologies in education in general and in teaching a foreign language (English), in particular, can be applied by a teacher at almost all stages of the educational process, in particular: in the preparation of theoretical material; in the creation of information and methodological support for the discipline; when developing demonstration materials for a lesson; when testing students' knowledge; for collecting and analyzing academic performance statistics. This list can be modified and expanded by the teacher in accordance with the specifics of the teaching activity.

Today we can already say that Internet technologies are part of the general information culture of teachers and students. The Internet stimulates children's desire to learn, expands the area of individual activity of each student, increases the speed of delivery of high-quality material within one lesson

The issue of integrating the Internet into education and, in particular, its use in teaching foreign languages, is currently quite relevant, since using the Internet as a means of teaching a foreign language is the best way to achieve many of the goals and objectives of teaching and upbringing.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are enormous. The global Internet network not only creates conditions for obtaining any information necessary for students and teachers, but also offers foreign language teachers many useful resources. These are special programs for teaching foreign languages, educational platforms, as well as authentic material, which the teacher can select independently and adapt to specific educational tasks.

As an example of work in this direction, I would like to cite a series of training sessions using ICT, which was conducted in the classroom on the topic "Man – the Child of Nature". During the series of sessions, Internet resources were used, as well as Power Point presentations made by the teacher and students during work on this topic.

To practice the vocabulary, as well as to develop listening and reading skills, the Internet resources (online assignments and work on projects) and the educational platform "Я класс" were used. At the end of the work, a press conference was organized on the Zoom platform with the participation of native speakers. The following equipment was used during the work: - in class – a computer with Internet access, a screen, tablets for students;

- for individual work of students – a phone/tablet, a computer with Internet access.

Below are the stages of the series of training sessions.

1. For introduction to the topic, the video clip “I Love You, Mother Nature” is used (https://yandex.ru/video/preview/text_«I_Love_You_Mother_Nature»_&path_wizard&parent_reqid_1615636547595923_75296135948364224)

While watching this video, students were asked to complete the task of recording facts that confirm the superiority of nature over man (individual work). Then, a discussion of the watched video was organized in groups, work on the content, vocabulary (individual, frontal work).

2. "Brainstorming". Which of the following activities harms nature and why? (work in pairs). Slide from the presentation prepared by the teacher for the lesson.

3. Using the exercises given in the textbook, vocabulary is introduced, on the basis of which further discussion of the problem will take place. To consolidate this vocabulary, online exercises are used, which students can complete from their phones by following the link. By working with these exercises individually, students see their results immediately. come back and try again. This way, the vocabulary on the topic is consolidated. Next comes the discussion of the most significant environmental issues. (frontal work).

A) [https://www.liveworksheets.com/worksheets/en/English_as_a_Second_Language_\(ESL\)/Environment/Environment_verbs_yz1401985tz](https://www.liveworksheets.com/worksheets/en/English_as_a_Second_Language_(ESL)/Environment/Environment_verbs_yz1401985tz)

4. Next we work with the text (online assignment). Upon completion of work on the text and completed assignments, students are asked to discuss the content of the text and find ways to solve the problem posed in the text.

5. In order to consolidate the material covered, students are invited to complete a number of training tasks on the educational platform "Я класс" (<https://www.yaklass.ru/TestWork/Results>)

Выбранные задания	Баллы	Выбранные задания	Баллы
^ v Reading. Environmental problems	3	^ v Listening. Climate change	4.5
^ v Reading. Environment	3	^ v Listening. A news report about global issues	4.5
^ v Reading. What happens to climate?	3	^ v Listening. Polar bears are in danger	4.5

6. The next stage is working on a project (pair or group work). Students use Internet resources, process information, design and present the results of their activities (Power Point Presentations). Listeners ask questions to the speakers.

7. The final stage of the work is a demonstration of the ability to apply the acquired skills in practice. A press conference “Save the World” is organized on the Zoom or Skype platform with the involvement of native speakers. This allows students to carry out real interaction and realize all the benefits of learning English.

In conclusion, I would like to note that ICT allows for a more complete implementation of a whole range of methodological, didactic, pedagogical and psychological principles, making the learning process more interesting and creative. The ability to take into account the levels of students' language proficiency is fundamental for implementing the principles of individualization and differentiated approach to learning.

At the same time, the principle of accessibility is observed and the individual pace of work of each student is taken into account. Using a computer and the Internet, it is possible to organize individual, paired and group forms of work in the lesson. The use of digital technologies in English lessons within reasonable limits allows for the implementation of part of the health technology that is so in demand in the lesson. However, it must be remembered that a computer cannot replace a teacher in the classroom. It is necessary to carefully plan the time spent working with a computer during the lesson and use it exactly when it is really necessary..

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